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Research Article

Evaluation of Health-Related Quality of Life in Geriatric Patients in A Tertiary Care Hospital

Shravani S, Shanila Thankam Suresh*, Nandini Goswami, Dr. Anjaly Sivakumar

Krupanidhi College of Pharmacy, Carmelaram, Karnataka, India.560035

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ABSTRACT

The assessment of health-related quality of life in elderly people is the main objective of the study. The validity of health-related quality of life as a measure of various disorders is becoming more widely accepted. A person's HRQOL is limited to the areas of their life that are impacted by their health, illness, and/or treatment. The primary objective is to measure the health-related quality of life of elderly patients who are admitted to a tertiary care hospital. The secondary objective is to ascertain the variables influencing elderly patients' health-related quality of life. There were 71 (59.17%) women and 49 (40.83%) men. The average age of patients was 60 ± 5 years. The physical health status showed lower score as compared to mental health component. From the logistic linear regression model analysis, age was found to be a significant predictor that affects quality of life in Geriatric patients. Patients in these risk categories should be closely watched for signs of deteriorating mental and physical health. The quality of life in the elderly population is greatly impacted by disease. Nonetheless, it was discovered that the most important determinants of mental health and deteriorating cognition were education, socioeconomic standing, and social background. Therefore, elderly patients in the aforementioned risk category should be closely watched in order to target and enhance their quality of life.

INTRODUCTION

Health-related quality of life (HRQOL) is increasingly acknowledged as a vital measure for assessing the impact of health conditions on individuals. HRQOL specifically focuses on aspects of a person's life influenced by health,

illness, or medical care and incorporates subjective perceptions of emotional, physical, and social well-being. It reflects an individual's personal evaluation and response to their health status.^{1,2}

Geriatrics is the medical specialty concerned with the clinical, preventive, therapeutic, and social aspects of illness in older adults. While individuals

*Corresponding Author: Shanila Thankam Suresh

Address: Krupanidhi College of Pharmacy, Carmelaram, Karnataka, India.560035

Email ✉: shanilasuresh@gmail.com

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aged 55 years and above are generally classified as geriatrics, this threshold is somewhat arbitrary, as physiological changes associated with aging are gradual and continuous rather than abrupt at a specific age. In some contexts, the geriatric population is defined as those aged 60 years and above.^{4, 8}

Aging poses one of the most significant health challenges globally, increasingly so due to advancements in medical therapies and technologies that has extended life expectancy. Notably, approximately 90% of elderly Americans report using at least one medication, underscoring the importance of pharmacological management in this group.⁹ Age-related alterations in pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics necessitate adjustments in medication use to accommodate changes in drug absorption, metabolism, distribution, and excretion.⁴

Age-associated physiological changes include slow muscle atrophy, with lean body mass declining by 20–30% between ages 30 and 80. Fat-free mass may decrease by 60–80%, while body fat percentage increases, particularly in men aged 18 to 36. Cellular mass diminishes by 30–65%, accompanied by a 20% reduction in the albumin pool. Cognitive decline begins around age 20 and progresses gradually until approximately 75 years of age. Motor function deterioration elevates the risk of accidents, and sensory impairments such as visual and auditory decline contribute to confusion. Collectively, these changes contribute to complex conditions commonly referred to as “old age syndromes”.^{4, 5}

HRQOL has emerged as an essential outcome measure for evaluating the efficacy of medical interventions. It is defined as an individual’s perception of their position in life within the cultural, social, and environmental contexts in which they live, relative to their goals,

expectations, and concerns.^{2, 3} The World Health Organization (WHO) developed the WHOQOL-100 to provide a comprehensive, cross-cultural quality of life assessment. Due to its length, a shorter instrument, the WHOQOL-BREF, comprising 26 items across four domains (physical health, psychological health, social relationships, and environment), was developed for practical application in large-scale studies.³

The possible raw score ranges for each domain are as follows:

- Physical Health=17
- Psychological=19
- Social Relationships=12
- Environment=30

The WHOQOL-BREF domains evaluate multiple dimensions: physical health includes mobility, pain, energy, and dependence on medical treatment; psychological health covers body image, self-esteem, and cognitive functions; social relationships assess sexual activity, social support, and interpersonal relations; and the environmental domain addresses safety, leisure activities, access to health services, and the physical environment.³

Need for study

India is experiencing a demographic transition with a rapidly aging population. In 2011, the elderly (60 years and above) comprised 8.6% of the population, a figure projected to reach 11.6% by 2026. Currently, the elderly population in India stands at approximately 153 million, representing about 10.51% of the total population. Given this demographic shift, evaluating the HRQOL among India’s elderly population is imperative to inform health policy and ensure effective resource allocation.

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee of MVJ Medical College and Research Hospital (Approval No. MVJMC&RH/IEC-122/2024, dated 21-02-2024).

Study Design

Cross-sectional observational study conducted on 120 geriatric patients admitted to general medicine, orthopedics, psychiatry, and general surgery departments.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients aged 60 years and above
- Patients admitted to the selected departments
- Both male and female patients
- Patients providing written informed consent

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients unwilling to participate
- Patients with severe cognitive impairment unable to answer the questionnaire
- Patients with terminal illness or in critical condition
- Patients admitted for less than 24 hours

Data Collection:

Quality of life of a patient was asked through questionnaire. Continuous data were introduced as Mean ± Standard deviation. Categorical data were given as frequencies rates for examination of quality of life; non-parametric test was done trailed by post-hoc investigation.

Data analysis was performed using Wilcoxon signed-rank test in SAS 9.4 through the univariate procedure and MS Excel was used to compare domain using a boxplot. Descriptive summary statistics are presented either as mean SD or as median (minimum and maximum). Statistical

significance of the comparison in response proportions was determined using a univariate procedure with QQ PLOT.

RESULT

Descriptive Summary of Demographics:

About 40.83% of the studied population were males, whereas 59.17% were females. Out of 120 patients studied, 50.83% were between the age of 60-69 years, 28.33% were between 70-79 years, 15% were between 80 - 89 years, and 5% were between 90- 99 years, 0.83% were between 100-105 years

Assessment of health-related quality of life WHO-BREF

While the WHO-QOL-100 has 100 questionnaires, the WHO-BREF scale only contains 26 verified questionnaires. Therefore, the WHO-BREF raw scores must be translated using the formula below to provide a value between 1 and 100:

$$\text{Transformed score} = (\text{Score}-4) \times (100/ 16).$$

Logistic linear regression models were used to identify clear determinants of domain scores on the WHO BREF scale. The following variables were taken into account as the independent predictors of domain scores for creating logistic linear regression models. To identify the predictors, the WHO-BREF scales' domain scores 1, 2, 3, and 4 were each individually regressed against the factors regarded as independent.

Table 1: Age wise distribution

Sr. No	Age In Years	No. of Patients (N=120)	Percentage Of Patients (%)
1	60-69	61	50.83
2	70-79	34	28.33
3	80-89	18	15
4	90-99	6	5

5	100	1	0.83
Total No. Of Patients		120	

Out of 120 patients, 61 patients (50.83%) were in the age group of 60-69years, 34 patients (28.33%) were in the age group of 70-79 years, 18 patients (15%) were in the age group of

80-89 years, 6 patients (5%) were in the age group of 90–99-year, 1 patient (0.83%) were in the age group of 100 years

Table 2: Gender wise distribution

Sr. No		No. Of Patients (n=120)	Percentage Of Patients (%)
1	Male	49	40.83
2	Female	71	59.17
Total No. of Patients		120	

Out of selected 120 patients, 49 patients (40.83%) were male and the remaining 71 patients (59.17%) were female

Table: 3 Domain score

Variable	N	Mean	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum	Median	Poor QOL n (%)
DOMAIN 1	120	20.40833333	3.6907693	11	28	21	41.77
DOMAIN2	120	18.28333333	3.3984260	8	27	18	39.13
DOMAIN 3	120	9.841666667	1.7100584	3	15	10	34.45
DOMAIN 4	120	26.15	6.03720955	10	40	26	34.68

Domain 1: Physical Health

The following things were evaluated in Domain 1, which deals with physical health:

Item no.	Item	Response				
		1	2	3	4	5
Q3	To what extent do you feel that physical pain prevents you from doing what you need to do?	3	27	58	30	2
Q4	How much do you need any medical treatment to function in your daily life?	1	20	63	35	1
Q10	Do you have enough energy for everyday life?	4	44	60	10	2
Q15	How well are you able to get around?		32	69	19	
Q16	How satisfied are you with your sleep?	3	49	30	29	9
Q17	How satisfied are you with your ability to perform your daily living activities?	1	18	83	16	2
Q18	How satisfied are you with your capacity for work?	2	41	56	20	1

WHOQOL-BREF domains

1. Daily tasks related to physical well-being that depend on medications and medical equipment job competence, mobility, energy consumption, pain, discomfort, sleep, and rest.
2. Emotional reactions to one's physical attributes, including positive and negative feelings, self-worth, spirituality, religion, and personal beliefs concentration, memory, learning, and reasoning.
3. Sexual activity, interpersonal relationships, social support, and social connections.
4. Funding for environmental freedom, physical safety, and security possibilities to learn new things, opportunities to participate in and discover leisure activities, accessibility and a decent living environment, and the physical environment (pollution, noise, traffic, and climate).

- 58 patients (48.3%) reported that they are unable to perform their daily tasks due to moderate physical pain.
- According to 63 patients (52.5%), they need a moderate amount of medical care on a daily basis.
- Sixty patients (50%) reported having a moderate quantity of energy for day-to-day activities.
- According to 69 patients (57.5%), they are neither poor nor adept at getting around.
- A quarter of the patients, or thirty, expressed dissatisfaction with their sleep.
- 56 patients, or 46.6%, said they are neither happy nor unhappy with their ability to work.

Domain 2: Psychological

The following things were evaluated in Domain 2, which deals with psychological health:

Item No.	Item	Response				
		1	2	3	4	5
Q5	How much do you enjoy life?	2	23	66	29	
Q6	To what extent do you feel your life to be meaningful?	1	23	75	20	1
Q7	How well are you able to concentrate?	2	29	56	31	2
Q11	Are you able to accept your bodily appearance?	2	22	74	21	1
Q19	How satisfied are you with yourself?		19	67	33	1
Q26	How often do you have negative feelings such as blue mood, despair, anxiety,	1	16	71	3	1

- 66 (55%) of the patients said they enjoy life to a moderate degree.
- 75 patients (62.5%) reported feeling that their lives have a moderate amount of purpose.
- 56 patients (46.6%) reported having moderate amounts and having trouble focusing.
- 74 patients, or 80.6%, said they accept their physical appearance to a moderate degree.
- 67 patients, or 55.8%, said they were neither happy nor unhappy with themselves.
- 71 (59.1%) patients stated that have negative Feelings such as blue moon despair, anxiety, depression quite often.

Domain 3: Social relationship

The following things were evaluated in Domain 3, which deals with Social relationship

Item no.	Item	Response				
		1	2	3	4	5
Q20	How satisfied are you with your personal relationships?	1	11	69	37	2
Q21	How satisfied are you with your sex life?	1	6	104	8	1
Q22	How satisfied are you with the support you get from your friends?	2	12	27		8

- 69 patients, or 57.5 percent, said they were neither happy nor unhappy with their personal connection.
- 104 (86.6%) of the patients said they were neither happy nor unhappy with their sexual lives.
- 71 patients, or 59.1%, say they are happy with their buddy support.

Domain 4: Environment

The following things were evaluated in Domain 4, which deals with Environment

Item no.	Item	Response				
		1	2	3	4	5
Q8	How safe do you feel in your daily life?	1	30	61	26	2
Q9	How healthy is your physical environment?	1	11	74	31	3
Q12	Have you enough money to meet your needs?	2	32	36	48	2
Q13	How available to you is the information that you need in your day-to-day life?	1	16	45	56	2
Q14	To what extent do you have the opportunity for leisure activities?	10	36	49	21	4
Q23	How satisfied are you with the conditions of your living place?		5	41	64	10
Q24	How satisfied are you with your access to health services?	1	15	37	47	20
Q25	How satisfied are you with your transport?	1	23	38	31	27

- 61 patients (47.5%) reported feeling moderately safe in their day-to-day activities.
- 74 patients, or 61.6%, reported feeling moderately healthy about their physical surroundings.
- 48(40%) of the patients said they generally have enough money to cover their expenses.
- 56 patients, or 46.6%, said that they largely had access to the information they require for their daily needs.
- 49 (35.2%) of the patients say they have a moderate quantity of leisure time.
- 64 (53.3%) of the patients expressed satisfaction with their living conditions.
- 47 patients, or 39.1%, expressed satisfaction with their access to medical care.
- 38 (31.6%) of the patients said they were neither happy nor unhappy with their transportation.

DISCUSSION

Health is a key indicator of life quality; both mental and physical health has a big impact on life quality [10]. Aging is regarded as the most difficult health issue globally and has emerged as a new health concern.

The creations of new medications and technological advancements have increased life expectancy.⁽⁹⁾ However, age is becoming a major factor influencing older patients' quality of life⁽⁵⁾.

A wide range of cognitive tests were used in this study, and the assessments were modified based on the students' educational background. Establishing interventions targeted at decreasing inactivity and enhancing or maintaining an individual's activity level and, consequently, quality of life depends on the early recognition of cognitive impairments.

The clinical trial performed by Prohazkaetal et.al, it was observed that lowest levels of physical activity are frequently associated with poorer socioeconomic position ⁽⁶⁾. In a cross-sectional survey which was performed by MaryarTarvaj et.al, results from a limited sample size that showed older Iranians in Tehran had a comparatively low HRQOL, especially older women and those with less education.⁽⁷⁾⁽⁸⁾

Elderly people's emotional and physical well-being is influenced by a number of things. In order to ascertain how illness impairment affected everyday activities and behavior, we employed the WHO-BREF and EQ-5D grading systems. The presence of co morbidities, financial situation,

marital status, and family type were found to have an impact on the quality of life of elderly patients as measured by the WHO-BREF scale's domain 1 scores. To identify predictors, four linear regression models were constructed for each domain; however, only the model with the highest prediction ability, as shown by the regression coefficient (r^2) value, was chosen.

We used a validated, multidimensional WHOQOL-BREF questionnaire to evaluate the health-related quality of life (HRQOL) of elderly individuals. The physical and psychological domains of HRQOL were found to be considerably degraded in a considerable fraction of the aged population.

LIMITATIONS

The study has certain limitations due to the study setting and financial constraints of investigation. Since the study was carried out in the presence of family members, the participant may not openly discuss their details, leading to self-reporting bias.

The possibility of incorrect responses of the participant due to recall can be expected due to age-related issues. The mixed method could be used to strengthen the current study findings.

However, after knowing the study was only for academic purposes, their side was reluctant for active participation.

CONCLUSION

The study reported there were nearly half of participants (41.77%) with poor health quality of life in physical health domain and 39.13% of elderly with poor quality of life in psychological domain. Multiple linear regression analysis revealed that older age, female, no schooling; without spouse, lower economic status and chronic disorder were independently associated with low

quality of life score. The present study reflected that quality of life related to health was poor among nearly half of elderly participants. It is well known fact that with the progression of age, the disorder and disability are part of life, though the disorder and disability cannot be prevented completely but family physician at the level of primary health care shall provide preventive and promotive measures to reduce the progression of disorder and disability among elderly, which would in turn lead to enhancement of their health status and as well as quality of life. Preventive and promotive measure at the level of primary care includes making aware of health-related schemes available to them and

Preventing and managing disorder of chronic nature via counseling

Future research is needed to explore HRQOL in broader elderly populations, including community-dwelling and rural elderly, and to examine the impact of targeted interventions or support systems on improving HRQOL over time. There is a negative association between age and quality of life scores. As age increases—especially beyond 70 years—the quality of life tends to decline, particularly in physical and psychological aspects. Older age groups reported more health limitations, dependence, emotional challenges, and reduced satisfaction with life.

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REFERENCES

1. Rajasi RS, Mathew T, Nujum ZT, Anish TS, Ramachandran R, Lawrence T. Quality of life

- and sociodemographic factors associated with poor quality of life in elderly women in Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala. *Indian J Public Health*. 2016;60(3):210–5. doi:10.4103/0019-557X.189016. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.4103/0019-557X.189016>
2. Kumar SG, Majumdar A, Pavithra G. Quality of life (QOL) and its associated factors using WHOQOL-BREF among elderly in urban Puducherry, India. *J Clin Diagn Res*. 2014 Feb;8(2):54–7. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3939587/>
 3. World Health Organization. WHOQOL-BREF: Introduction, Administration, Scoring and Generic Version of the Assessment. Programme on Mental Health. Geneva: World Health Organization; 1996. Available from: http://www.who.int/mental_health/media/en/76.pdf. [Last accessed on 2017 Aug 17].
 4. Mangoni AA, Jackson SHD. Age-related changes in pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics: basic principles and practical applications. *Br J Clin Pharmacol*. 2004 Jan;57(1):6–14. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1884523/>
 5. Hudakova A, Hornakova A. Mobility and quality of life in elderly and geriatric patients. *Int J Nurs Midwifery*. 2011;3(5):57–62. Available from: <https://academicjournals.org/journal/IJNM/article-full-text-pdf/902246A924>
 6. McAuley E, Konopack JF, Motl RW, Morris KS, Doerksen SE, Rosengren KR. Physical activity and quality of life in older adults: influence of health status and self-efficacy. *Ann Behav Med*. 2006;31(1):99–103. Available from: https://link.springer.com/article/10.1207/s15324796abm3101_14
 7. Tajvar M, Arab M, Montazeri A. Determinants of health-related quality of life in elderly in Tehran, Iran. *BMC Public Health*. 2008;8:323. doi:10.1186/1471-2458-8-323. Available from: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/1471-2458-8-323>
 8. Barua A, Mangesh R, Kumar HH, Mathew S. A cross-sectional study on quality of life in geriatric population. *Indian J Community Med*. 2007;32(2):146. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2781125>
 9. Kaufman DW, Kelly JP, Rosenberg L, Anderson TE, Mitchell AA. Recent patterns of medication use in the ambulatory adult population of the United States: the Slone survey. *JAMA*. 2002;287(3):337–44. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.287.3.337>
 10. The EuroQol Group. EuroQol—a new facility for the measurement of health-related quality of life. *Health Policy*. 1990;16(3):199–208. Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-8510\(90\)90421-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-8510(90)90421-9)

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